

**HUMAN EYE DETECTION SYSTEM FOR RECOGNIZE
EYE DISEASES USING IMAGE PROCESSING**

A SYNOPSIS

Submitted by

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1. INTRODUCTION

The eye detection or eye tracker is the sensor technology that permits a device to get to know distinctly where our eyes are focused, and it regulates our presence, attention, drowsiness, consciousness, and other fatigue states. This intelligence shall be used for acquiring the deep accurate and understanding in to consumer behavior or to model the new interfaces across diverse devices. When comes to eye tracking in the real world the three factors comes to our mind that is construed the human behavior, allows hand free interplay, and user experiences of the humanized user interfaces. By adjoining the eye tracking with other input modules, for instance keyboard, mouse, and voice. Employing the eyes as a pointer at a screen the methods of eye tracking facilitates interoperation with nodes and other gadgets when the user unable to resort their hands as an input form. Iris localization could be a prime associate degreeed 1st stage in an iris recognition rule which involves detection of iris boundaries. The iris localization is followed by stages of iris standardization, feature extraction and iris-template matching, but the iris localization is most time consuming stage in an iris recognition system with finite (limited) database size [1,2]. The evolution of small cost and small size embedded systems for the iris recognition is the present concern of research development, where the avail of moderate speed and low power gadgets that central processing units (CPUs) is favorable [3,4]. The committed hardware system for iris recognition and localization task is very beneficial for the embedded iris recognition and pupil detection systems to attain the performance of real time systems, since iris localization is a prolonging task as pointed earlier. The generation of edge map is not mere an edge sensing step; it also entails image preliminary preprocessing steps, particularly for the iris localization and detection of slighter constrained images. The routinely employed techniques that are availed in the edge-map generation for iris pupil detection comprises threshold value, morphological techniques, canny, Sobel edge discernment, image filtering

techniques, reflection withdrawal and image quality enhancement etc. The edge-map generation turns in to dominant feature in the iris localization and pupil detection algorithms when image based data having lighting reflections, erratic illumination, and low contrast.

Eye Pupil tracking system developed in [5] is interested in indicating the spot of pupil area of eye during live video

- Saccadic eye movements while face is stationary
- Eyes are stationary
- Eyes are making open and close vice versa.

1.1 Image Processing

In image processing it is essential to filter the each frame so that blur or noise in the image is alleviated while restoring as much as viable. As like starburst algorithm we embark the process of eye camera image along with gaussian filter to mitigate the noise of image. The Gaussian filters are beneficial in mitigating noise sensitive to any algorithm that exploits gradient information. In addition the dividable nature of 2D Gaussian allows effective implementation. Mostly the noise in video or image begets using OTS cameras is because of lossy compression. The lossy compression algorithm shall be anticipated to pose some sensitive artifacts in the motion video. As number of artifacts is empowered the videos could turn in to more compressed. The algorithms we have used here specifically became to permit artifacts as long as they just simply noticeable. It is commonly known as merely noticeable difference. The image processing methods are typically much sensitive to the artifacts than the human eye. In most shortened schemes bifurcate the image in to tiny blocks and perform a conversion of each block separately. The elements within the block are rounded. As adjacent blocks are different we are left with borders with small edges. There are inopportune borders poses wise gradients that cover the sharp gradients with the edges of the desirable factors. The

Gaussian filter smoothens the picture removing highly localized gradients the gradients which are wiser are blurred but not ousted. In starburst the complete gradient picture has not profited instead calculated during traits detection. It was conceived that processing a mitigated computation. Though gradient assessing is barely a driven one which is analogous to Gaussian smoothing and evolves with the derivative of the Gaussian. We have chosen to facilitate implementation by computing the gradient.

1.2 Edge Detection Techniques

There are various methods to execute edge detection. Nevertheless, the majority of distinct methods may be organized into two subjects:

Gradient: One of the gradient methods notices the edges by seeking for the maximum and minimum values in the first derivative of the image.

Laplacian: The Laplacian method looks for the zero crossings in the first and second derivative of the snap to detect edges. An edge has one-dimensional structure of a ramp and quantifying the second hand of the image can spot out its location.

1.2.1 Sobel Edge Detection

The Sobel operator method is employed in image processing technique, especially within the edge detection algorithms. Formally, the Sobel operator method is a distinct differentiation operator, determining an estimation of the gradient of the image greatness function. At every point of the image, the outcome of the Sobel operator method is either the analogous gradient vector, or the standard of this vector. The Sobel operator relies on convolving the image with a tiny low, separable, and number valued filter in horizontal and vertical direction and is thus comparatively cheap in computations. On the other hand, the gradient approximation which it produces is relatively crude, in particular for high frequency variations in the image.

In clear terms, the Sobel detection operator computes the gradient of the image acuteness at every point in an image, giving the regulation of the largest

feasible soar from light to dark and the rank of deviation in that direction. The outcome therefore exhibits how well "abruptly" or "smoothly" the image deviates at that specific point and as a result how probably it is that part of the image specifies an edge, as well as how the edge detection algorithm is likely to be oriented. In operation, the immensity (likelihood of an edge) calculation is more authentic and easier to elucidate than the direction determination.

$$h_x = \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 0 & 1 \\ -2 & 0 & 2 \\ -1 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad h_y = \begin{bmatrix} -1 & -2 & -1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 2 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

Figure 1: Sobel edge detector mask

2. OBJECTIVES AND SCOPE OF THE WORK

The scope of this thesis works are

1. To detect human eye pupil region with limited computational complexity.
2. To remove noises using Gaussian filter and Median filter
3. To find pupil region using Morphological dilation and sobel operator.
4. To implement in an FPGA with low area resources.

This method alleviates the fictitious edges extremely in the edge-map of eye image, which is favorable for the sure and fast pupil detection. Field programmable logic array (FPGA) oriented hardware implementation of the proposed methods is suggested, which can be employed in iris localization and pupil detection system on FPGA based principles for iris pupil recognition application.

3. REVIEW OF LITERATURE WORK

Eye tracking is a technique used in perceptive science, iris recognition [6], human-computer Interaction [7], advertising, medical research, and other areas. One simple method [8] is a camera focused on eye and recording their

movements as the observer looks at some kind of stimulus and then these records are processed by image processing software. Most of the modern [9],[10] systems use infrared beams to create corneal reflection, from which the angle of measure can be calculated. Most of them use a frequency of at least 30Hz to capture the details of the very rapid eye movements.

In [11] Zhu and Q. Ji proposed different eye detection methods like template, appearance, and feature based methods. The eyes were exactly detecting in these methods and it is expensive in computational part. In [12], author given details about a fast eye detection scheme for use in video streams. In [13], author developed a face detection algorithm using MCT and Ada Boost. In [14], author developed an eye detection method using AdaBoost training with MCT-based eye features. A tiny low example known as structuring component. This structuring component is applied to any or all doable locations of the input image and generates identical size output. In this operation the outcome of the image pixel values are originated on same pixels of the input image with its neighbors. This operation creates a novel binary image in which if test is effective it would have non-zero pixel values at the specific location in the input image. There are various structuring elements like diamond shaped, square shaped, cross shaped etc. IMAGE contrast enhancement is important in medical applications. This is due to the fact that visual examination of medical images is essential in the diagnosis of many diseases. In applications such as chest radiography and mammography [15], [16], the image contrast is inherently low due to the small differences in the X-ray attenuation coefficients. Linear contrast stretching and histogram equalization are two widely utilized methods for global image enhancement [17]–[18]. In diagnostic medical images, local details may be more important than global contrast. Adaptive histogram equalization (AHE) [19]–[20] and adaptive contrast enhancement (ACE) [21]–[22] are two well-known local

enhancement methods. AHE algorithms map the grey values of pixels victimisation the relationships obtained from the native histograms. Although this improves image contrast, it requires intensive computations [23]. The bilinear interpolation technique was developed [24] to reduce the computational burden. It first divides images into blocks, and then calculates the mapping functions of those blocks.

4. METHODOLOGIES

The Pupil detector receives the image from the different data standard iris database and detects pupil on the image. Here I used 640*480 resolutions for pupil detection. After received the clear image, image processing algorithm is to be applied. Median filter is used to reduce the salt and pepper noise meanwhile Gaussian filter is used to smoothen the image. Then proper threshold is applied to convert black and white image. So that easily can detect black region in an image. Spatial and temporal filters are used to find out the exact pupil regions in an eye. Finally centroid is calculated to track the pupil in moving conditions.

4.1 Image Processing

After received image from database then applied to an image processing block. This block contains black and white image conversion, filters, pupil detection algorithm. Based on optimum threshold value here is 30 for human image. Above the threshold value 30 is set to 1 and below values are set to 0 a pupil. Morphological dilation is used twice to eliminate extra illumination and unwanted eye lids. Sobel filter is applied to find out the exact pupil region edges on eye.

Figure 2 Flow diagram for pupil detection

In Figure 2 explains the flow of pupil detection methodologies with Gaussian filter. Original image is filtered by Gaussian filter to smooth the original image. Original image is filtered by median filter to remove noises present in original image. Proper threshold is applied on filtered image to separate the pupil region. Here I used threshold value is 30. Dilation process is involved to remove extra eyelashes and eyelids. Finally Sobel filter has given clear pupil region.

4.2 Cyclone II FPGA Development Board

On board 50 MHz clock is used to generate 25 MHz VGA clock from PLL. Mega wizard plugin manager is utilized to generate PLL clock. From memory output, data's are given to image processing block. This block will do

pupil detection process. Image processed data given to VGA display. FPGA plays an major role and controls all the hardware interfaces.

4.3 Comparison Table

Table 1: Proposed Device utilization for Altera Cyclone IV FPGA

Logic utilization	Used /Avail		Utilization (%)	
	Existing work (virtex 5)	Proposed work (cyclone II)	Existing work (virtex 5)	Proposed work (cyclone II)
Total logic elements/Slices	45,716 /207,360	6,151 / 33,216	22%	19 %
Total combinational functions / LUT's	133,916/ 207,360	5,070 / 33,216	64%	15 %
Dedicated logic registers/ slices	39,914 / 51,840	2,899 / 33,216	76%	9 %
Total memory bits	288 /10,368	55,936/ 483,840	2%	12 %

Comparison table 1 gives Xilinx and Altera platforms FPGA's results. From this table logic elements utilization is reduced 3% in proposed system. Total combinational LUT's are also reduced from 64% to 15%. Memory utilization is increased in proposed because of SDRAM utilization.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

5.1 Altera Quartus II Synthesis Results

Figure 3: Logic utilization summary

Figure 4: RTL Design view

Figure 3, Figure 4 shows the Logic utilization summary and RTL Design view of Cyclone II EP2C35F672C6 device. Among 33,216 logic elements, the proposed design has taken 6,151 logical elements (19%).

Figure 5 Chip planner summary

	Clock Name	Type	Period	Frequency	Rise	Fall	Duty Cycle	Divide by	N
1	altera_reserved_tck	Base	100.000	10.0 MHz	0.000	50.000			
2	CLOCK_27	Base	37.000	27.03 MHz	0.000	18.500			
3	CLOCK_50	Base	20.000	50.0 MHz	0.000	10.000			
4	u1 altpll_component pll clk[0]	Generated	8.000	125.0 MHz	0.000	4.000	50.00	2	5
5	u1 altpll_component pll clk[1]	Generated	8.000	125.0 MHz	-3.000	1.000	50.00	2	5
6	u1 altpll_component pll clk[2]	Generated	10.000	100.0 MHz	0.000	5.000	50.00	1	2
7	u2 altpll_component pll clk[1]	Generated	24.666	40.54 MHz	0.000	12.333	50.00	2	3

Figure 6 Clock summary

Figure 5 and Figure 6 shows the Chip planner summary and clock summary of Cyclone device.

6. CONCLUSION

Eye detection is the beginning of the iris recognition system that is very effectively to be applied in medical equipment's like Non-contact tonometer, Fundus , Optical coherence Tomography etc. In order to detect eyes with

different sizes without so much computational work and without using databases of different sizes for each image, I have developed a threshold based pupil detection method. Eye tracking and eye movement analysis may be particularly interesting for the applications depending on user-computer dialogue since they represent measures which can provide valuable information about the visual and attention aspects of human. In this work, here proposed dedicated hardware architecture for eye detection. In order to detect eyes with different sizes without so much computational work and without using databases of different sizes for each image, I have developed a threshold based pupil detection method. Pupil detection is experimentally tested with 100 human eyes which gives 95% result successfully. Hardware reduction is also improved than existing method.

7. ORGANIZATION OF THE THESIS

The thesis is systematized as follows:

Chapter 1 Discusses the overview of Human Eye structure, different Eye Tracking technique, objective and scope of the work.

Chapter 2 Deals with Literature survey of various pupil detection methods and image processing techniques involved in this chapter in detail.

Chapter 3 Explains about Image enhancement using Gaussian filter and Median filter with its hardware implementation. EDA tool specification is also discussed in this chapter.

Chapter 4 Discusses about the Morphological operations with image enhancement for identifying pupil region in an iris image. The equations are optimized for digital implementation.

Chapter 5 Shows the results are presented in their sub-modules and then all the modules are combined to give the final output.

Chapter 6 Consists of conclusion, Limitation and further improvement on this work.

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